

On Applying Machine Learning to Develop Air Combat Simulation Agents

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Abstract

This paper describes several approaches for utilizing machine learning technologies towards improving the capabilities of autonomous, simulation-based agents. For an autonomous agent to be robust, it must be able to plan its activities, react quickly to unforeseen events, and execute planned or modified behaviors to achieve goals. We have begun to develop autonomous agents which exhibit appropriate behaviors for simulated air combat, providing intelligent, realistic adversaries and cooperative allies. Building such agents is not trivial, and the techniques of machine learning hold great promise for extending the capabilities of hand-coded systems. In this paper we describe the application of some of these techniques, past successes, and current research directions.

1 Introduction

1.1 The simulation environment

At the Air Force Institute of Technology (AFIT), we have been developing autonomous agents to serve as part of a distributed simulation architecture hosted on standard workstations, communicating through a high-speed network and accessed through virtual reality interfaces. Our efforts support the Advanced Research Projects Agency's (ARPA) Distributed Interactive Simulation (DIS) program [1] and computer generated forces efforts which will provide technology for integrated, real-time, combat simulation of a wide range of military forces at several different command levels. Our piece of the puzzle is to implement the basic capabilities for autonomous aircraft agents which can operate in stand-alone or distributed simulations. The current capabilities of our prototype MAXIM, although modest, were developed as a vehicle for a variety of research thrusts [2].

In this simulation environment the autonomous agents must maintain a real-time pace in the midst of network communication delays, information losses, computer resource competition, and the uncertainties inherent in interacting with humans. This ability embodies a fundamental philosophy of the DIS program: information cannot be expected to flow smoothly, so the agents must interpolate, project, and otherwise compensate for missing information, updating themselves to known states and clock times when such information does arrive. It also means that successive

simulations cannot be expected to unfold identically. Since there is an inherent nondeterminism in this approach, any mechanism attempting to improve the capabilities of the agents must provide robust solutions. This is certainly an ambitious requirement, but one rich in valuable research potential and exciting to pursue. The parallel to the human practice of acquiring experience about a domain to handle such uncertainties has not gone unnoticed. It is this parallel we seek to exploit with machine learning.

The simulation-based environment provides a rich vehicle for automated learning for a variety of aspects of air combat. For example, within a simulation of reasonable fidelity a system could learn to improve skill-level behaviors such as the ability to fly closer to the edge of the aircraft's flight envelope, or optimization of quality of ride measures. However, we are more interested in higher-level behaviors: the decision-making processes involved in determining what actions to perform and when to execute them. Therefore, we view an autonomous agent as a collection of low-level procedures to execute actions, with both reactive and generative planning capabilities to provide the high-level guidance. The reactive component is essentially a large table of responses to recognizable situations, known as a *universal plan* [3]. For any possible situation, a plan can always be found; it is the quality or appropriateness of the plan which varies with the situation. This is a fundamental and unavoidable characteristic of reactive, or rapid-response, planning. Generative planning, the ability to construct plans based upon sound reasoning techniques and an understanding of the cause-and-effect relationships within a domain (relationships between plans and goals, or the knowledge of how actions effect state changes), is useful in situations when the environment does not demand an immediate response. This can occur within a simulation during relatively quiet times and is a natural component of long-range planning. Generative planning is also quiet useful to leverage during non-interactive, non-real-time simulation as the basis for several forms of machine learning, with the goal of improving the universal plan.

1.2 Machine learning strategies

Five machine learning techniques with immediate applicability in a simulation environment are explanation-based learning, chunking from generative planning, discovery-based learning, genetic (or classi-

fication) algorithms, and constructive induction. The interaction of MAXIM with a human or another simulation (such as another copy of MAXIM) can provide the necessary learning situations.

Explanation-based learning (EBL¹) is a technique that relies on extensive background knowledge (the domain theory) and a single learning situation (training example) provided in some fashion by a teacher [4, 5]. The success of EBL rests on two assumptions: the example is accurate and significant, and the knowledge base is sufficiently rich to be able to "understand" the new situation in terms of previous experiences. EBL has been applied for the acquisition of tactical planning knowledge for air combat operations in the Air Force sponsored Learning Systems for Pilot Aiding (LSPA) program, in which a pilot operates a flight simulator and the system attempts to predict his actions [6]. The highest-level goal of the system is to continually provide the pilot with the information relevant to the current context: correct prediction of the pilot's actions serve to ratify its understanding of the context. When the system fails in prediction, the learning component is invoked with the pilot's actions in the current situation serving as the training example. Upon analyzing and understanding the pilot's actions, this new experience is added to the knowledge base to aid in future predictions. Although LSPA concentrated on acquiring knowledge to improve the ability of an associate system (an electronic crewmember) to aid a pilot, such an approach could easily be adapted to the development of autonomous agents. The LSPA program demonstrated the technical feasibility of this approach for acquisition of tactical planning knowledge.

Chunking refers to the compilation and memorization of a new plan resulting from generative planning. It is similar to EBL, except that the learning instance is not an example provided by a teacher, but rather occurs when the system is not able to find a simple response to the situation within its current set of known plans. The system attempts to find a reactive solution, reaches an *impasse*, applies generative planning to overcome the impasse, and chunks the solution around the impasse for future use. This approach is the modus operandi of the SOAR system [7], and is being applied to the development of intelligent autonomous agents by other researchers [8]. Although potentially infeasible during real-time, interactive simulation due to the indeterminacy of the time spent during generative planning, this approach is quite useful for improvement of the universal plan "off-line." With a sufficiently robust universal plan, generative planning may be seldom required.

Discovery-based learning (DBL) and genetic algorithms (GA) are approaches that require no human interaction. As long as some environment exists to provide feedback to measure the quality of proposed "knowledge," these techniques will work to improve a system's overall performance through heuristically-guided generation and test (i.e., trial and error). An automated simulation environment, such as two copies of MAXIM battling each other, can provide this feed-

back. Both the DBL and GA approaches propose new knowledge as refinements of existing knowledge, evaluate the resultant behaviors with respect to the environment and alternative behaviors, and retain the most promising knowledge as the basis of further refinement. DBL uses heuristics for modifying existing knowledge (e.g., increase/decrease parameters, reverse terms, reorder operations). The GA approach generates new knowledge by making syntactic modifications to the existing knowledge through operations such as cut-and-splice and mutation.

Through knowledge engineering, we have identified maneuvers which are useful in situations that are currently not represented in the universal plan [9, 10, 11]. For example, there are several maneuvers designed to maintain an aircraft's total energy (sum of potential and kinetic energies) such as the low- and high-speed yo-yo's and the Immelman. Aircraft energy is an important feature that can be derived from measurable data, but MAXIM currently has no plans which are triggered by considerations of energy. The correlation of energy information to plan applicability is an area in which *constructive induction* may be useful. Inductive methods use several training examples to provide a basis for informed generalization: from the examples, an inductive system would identify which of the characteristics appear useful for recognizing the desired concept or situation. Constructive induction is a method of combining simple characteristics into more complex structures that may be necessary for this recognition [12, 13]. One example might be the assessment of an aircraft's kinetic energy based on a combination of measurable quantities such as velocity and acceleration vectors.

1.3 Current research

The remainder of this paper describes the research approaches currently being undertaken by two graduate students at AFIT. Section 2 discusses Capt Mezera's use of discovery-based learning to incorporate energy-management functions into the universal plan of MAXIM agents. Section 3 describes Capt Gordon's research in applying genetic algorithms to develop a rule-base for providing high-level control to MAXIM-like agents in a distributed simulation.

2 Discovery-based learning

2.1 The MAXIM world

Discovery-based learning is one possible approach that could be used to improve upon an agent's existing universal plan. DBL systems do not require human interaction and learning can begin with very little domain knowledge. Instead, a DBL system uses a set of heuristics to propose, select, and perform experiments in a simulated world as the system attempts to learn characteristics of that world. One of the most widely recognized discovery programs, AM, was able to derive complex mathematical concepts using heuristics to suggest which concepts were interesting and provide new concepts for exploration [14]. More recently, a researcher at AFIT has used DBL to develop threat avoidance maneuvers in MAVERICK, a simulator similar to MAXIM, demonstrating the ability to autonomously create a set of robust maneuver

¹We follow the customary practice of equating explanation-based learning with explanation-based generalization.

templates for reactive route replanning around unforeseen ground-based threats [15]. Previous success with DBL, combined with the fact that MAXIM provides an interesting dynamic world in which to experiment, has motivated us to investigate using DBL as a learning mechanism for enlarging MAXIM's universal plan.

The current version of MAXIM operates in one of three phases and performs actions which are applicable to that phase. Depending on the presence of a target aircraft or threatening missile, an agent's phase will be *search*, *attack*, or *evade* [3]. MAXIM agents always fly directly towards the target aircraft using proportional control, firing a missile at the target as soon as the minimum range constraints have been met. While this type of control is sometimes used by pilots, there are many other behaviors that are appropriate in other situations. A pilot may launch a missile at a target as soon as the aircraft is within range, but might then maneuver for position behind in case the missile doesn't destroy the target. All other things being equal, an agent that relies solely on proportional control would not always be able to achieve a positional advantage, and would rarely be victorious against a skilled opponent.

Figure 1 illustrates one instance when proportional control is inappropriate. In this scenario, the agent and the target are initially traveling along parallel headings. The agent is traveling at lower velocity than the target aircraft and consequently has a smaller turning radius, but fails to use this difference to its advantage. A classic maneuver known as the 'flat scissors,' shown in Figure 2, could have been used to achieve a better end-game position for the agent than is possible with proportional control [9].

Figure 1: MAXIM's proportional control is sometimes inappropriate. In this scenario, the agent overshoots the target and loses the opportunity to achieve a positional advantage.

A desired outcome of this research is to make MAXIM behavior not only less predictable, but more realistic. Through DBL, we would like MAXIM to learn a variety of behaviors during the *attack* phase that increase the probability of victory through maneuvers and energy management techniques. Energy management techniques are maneuvers designed to maintain the total energy of an aircraft, while allowing

Figure 2: Using the flat scissors, the agent could have made use of its shorter turning radius to get behind the target.

one form of energy to be converted to the other. For example, an aircraft at higher altitude than a target may trade a portion of that altitude for an increase in velocity in order to close in on the target. Likewise, to prevent his/her aircraft from overshooting the target, a pilot may put the aircraft in a climb, decreasing aircraft velocity for an increase in potential energy.

2.2 Factors affecting plan selection

To make MAXIM a more effective opponent during the *attack* phase, it is necessary to examine the domain and identify the parameters which are important to a pilot during flight combat. A skilled pilot will be able to take into account many different parameters before choosing his next response, but there might only be a handful of especially critical variables. Reducing the number of these parameters will be helpful during the learning phase, at which time the system must determine what effect each experiment has had on their resultant values.

In the case of MAXIM, an improvement in performance might be achieved if we select responses from the universal plan based on the following parameters: angle between fighter's line-of-sight and the target's direction of travel (aspect angle), fighter to target separation (range), relative altitude and closure rate. During the discovery process, a DBL mechanism that operates by modifying these parameters could experiment with the possible tradeoffs in potential and kinetic energy, possibly learning the worth of energy management functions for itself. We believe that a universal plan incorporating these features would be less predictable and more robust than one that used the same tactic under all circumstances.

2.3 Learning approach

To extend MAXIM's universal plan during the *attack* phase, we propose to train an agent in a lvl combat scenario. The target aircraft will initially be a level-flying, non-jinking bogey moving at constant velocity. MAXIM agents are normally quite aggressive, hurtling straight toward an opponent and firing a missile as soon as minimum range constraints are met. During learning, however, the ability to fire these all-aspect missiles will be disabled. Instead, the agent will be attempting to achieve a positional advantage over the target, placing it at the proper range and angle for a rear-quarter shot. All-aspect weapons capability will be restored when the learning phase has

been completed, but training with this capability off will give MAXIM an opportunity to learn contingency plans.

MAXIM will be set up to test possible responses for variations in aspect angle, closure rate, range, and relative altitude. As shown in Figure 3, every 30 degree increment in aspect angle defines a *plan sector* for which there can be several possible universal plan responses. Within sectors, plan selection will be further broken down based on range to the target (range1 or range2), relative altitude from the target (above or below), and closure rate towards the target (positive or negative). This will give MAXIM a total of 96 plan responses. It should be possible, however, to use the symmetry of fighter-target geometry to our advantage, teaching MAXIM only 24 responses in two octants of the sphere surrounding the target aircraft. In this case, the remaining 72 plan responses could be considered vector transformations of the 24 basic ones. After examining flight training documents and discussing the problem with an F-4 pilot, we believe that dividing the plan into segments at this resolution should be adequate for an improvement in agent behavior [10, 11].

Figure 3: The attack response chosen by an agent depends primarily on which plan sector the agent is in. Responses are further refined on the basis of closure rate, range, and relative altitude

Before learning begins, each of the 96 plan responses will be initialized so that MAXIM will fly directly towards the target. This will guarantee that the default behavior of the learning version of MAXIM is at least as good as the standard version. During learning, however, scenarios will be executed so that MAXIM may experiment with alternatives for each response. Alternative responses will take the form of repositioning the *fly-to* point of the MAXIM agent which, in the case of proportional control, is exactly equal to the current location of the target. Responses may also be modified by suggesting changes in the

magnitude of the agent's acceleration vector. By moving the fly-to point to some other position relative to the target, and adjusting aircraft power settings, we believe that MAXIM agents will learn other types of pursuit such as *lead* and *lag*, and when these types of behaviors are appropriate. In addition, we expect that the agent will learn energy management maneuvers by selecting fly-to points that are above and below the target aircraft.

2.4 DBL system architecture

In this section, we discuss a possible architecture for a DBL system that uses MAXIM as the simulated world. A block diagram of this architecture is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: A possible architecture for discovering air combat maneuvers in MAXIM

An important structure in AM and MAVERICK was the *agenda*. The agenda is a priority queue of maneuver experiments to try next, rank ordered according to their *interestingness*. Interestingness is simply a measure of a particular experiment's worth based on a set of scoring heuristics. Experiments that have received the highest scores spawn additional experiments that are explored first. This allows experimentation to continue along paths that appear to have the highest probability for success.

The success or failure of responses will be measured using a set of interestingness heuristics appropriate for the flight combat domain. Since our goal is to let MAXIM find ways to achieve an advantageous end-game position, behind the target and in position for a second shot at the target, a subset of the heuristics to guide experimentation might be:

- If the minimum aspect angle during this simulation is smaller than any other aspect angle experienced thus far, add a bonus.
- If the minimum aspect angle decreased during this simulation from the previous simulation, add a bonus.
- If the time to maneuver into the minimum aspect angle and range position was shorter than any other time experienced thus far, add a bonus.

- If the fighter stayed in the rear-quarter of the target throughout the simulation, add a bonus.
- If the fighter overshot the target flight path, subtract a penalty.
- If the fighter ever flew in front of the target, subtract a penalty.

Following a simulation run, the interestingness of a maneuver will be assessed using a set of heuristics similar to those mentioned above. Then, the system will suggest transformations to the maneuver using a second set of heuristics called *response heuristics*. This technique was used previously in the MAVERICK system to improve the flight time and decrease radar coverage of an aircraft flying through an area populated with SAM sites. The response heuristics will suggest adjustments to the fly-to point relative to the target aircraft, and suggest an increase or decrease in the power setting. The fly-to point adjustments will be akin to a unit vector adjustment, so that the actual adjustment made during simulation can be multiplied by the relative velocities of the two aircraft. Using this approach, the actual position of the fly-to point can be shifted ahead of or behind the target, depending on the agent's rate of closure. Scalable fly-to points will also allow MAXIM to generalize the tactics somewhat, so that a universal plan response learned for a specific training example can be applied to many other situations.

As an example, a subset of the response heuristics might be:

- If the fighter overshot the target, try decelerating the plane a little.
- If the target outran the fighter, try accelerating the plane a little.
- If the fighter flew in front of the target, move the fly-to point behind the target.
- If to achieve minimum range is increasing, move the fly-to point in front of the target.

The response heuristics may suggest one or several new responses to try next. Each suggested response will be assigned the interestingness value of the parent response, and will then be placed in a queue of pending responses. The system selects what appears to be the most promising response from the queue and the cycle repeats.

Theoretically, experimentation could continue indefinitely, but for practicality learning will be stopped after some threshold of interestingness has been achieved or the cycle has repeated a specified number of times. At that point, the best response tested so far becomes the response for that portion of the universal plan. The system is reset and learning begins for the next universal plan response.

2.5 Credit assignment

One problem this system could experience deals with the credit assignment issue. We intend to use DBL to learn responses starting from small aspects angles (agent approaching from the rear of the target aircraft) to larger ones. If the end-game position is to have the agent closing in for a second shot at the rear of the target, some maneuvers will eventually activate responses previously learned in other plan sectors. This approach gives the system the opportunity to build upon previously learned segments of the universal plan, but it is possible that the agent will be unable to find the best response for a starting position because a previously learned response is inadequate.

Our initial approach will be to assume that credit for success or failure of a response being tested belongs entirely to that response: previously learned responses activated along the way provide the correct behavior. This is a heuristic used in everyday life. When we learned to drive a car, we probably first practiced starting the engine in the driveway and tested the effect of pressing on the accelerator. Later, a parent took us out for a drive around the neighborhood, and soon we were driving on busy city streets. Each period of learning built on previously learned knowledge. Of course, there are times when previously learned knowledge proves to be incomplete, such as knowing to steer into a turn while skidding, or resisting the temptation to lock the brakes on an icy street. A universal plan to drive a car could perform well most of the time, even if we failed to train for these specialized conditions. During our research, however, we may determine that previously learned responses should be extended to account for these "exceptions to the rule."

2.6 Implementation

MAXIM is written in CLOS, the Common Lisp Object System, so it seemed natural to integrate the DBL mechanism into the simulator using the same language. We have also considered implementing the experimentation component of the system in the Soar architecture. Soar is a proposed general model of human cognition that attempts to satisfy goals using the *problem space hypothesis*. This hypothesis states that all problem solving can be accomplished by selecting a sequence of operators that defines a path from some initial state to a goal state.[7]

There is a great deal of similarity in the problem solving method implemented in Soar and models of the human process of discovery [16]. The experimentation process can be seen as repeated problem solving within problem spaces for generating, selecting, conducting, and assessing the outcome of experiments. Problem solving within some top level problem space, such as *experiment-world*, could repeat until a desired experimental outcome has been reached.

Connecting Soar to the external world provided by MAXIM may not be a trivial matter. Passing data back and forth between Soar and an external program is done through working-memory augmentations to the state [7], which may prove to be too clumsy for the amount of communication necessary between MAXIM and the DBL system. We are continuing to investigate the practicality of a Soar/MAXIM connection.

3 Genetic algorithms

3.1 Genetic algorithm operations

Another approach we are researching uses *genetic algorithms* (GA) to perform the discovery learning function. Genetic algorithms maintain a population of candidate solutions and improve performance by processing this population *en masse* using random genetic-like operators such as crossover and mutation [17]. These candidate solutions generally consist of parameter sets or rule structures, and are modified using the genetic operators to create new candidates. Central to this approach is the ability to assign a value or *fitness* to each candidate solution. The fitness measure is used to select which candidate solutions provide genetic material (parts of themselves) to build up the next generation. This fitness measure is similar in purpose to the interestingness heuristic of the DBL approach. The random, yet fitness-driven, manipulation of promising genetic material into new candidate solutions is how the GA "discovers" or "learns" new solutions.

The information a candidate solution embodies must be encoded in a way amenable to genetic manipulation. The representations mentioned above, parameter sets and rule structures, are both being investigated for use in agent development. The parameter set encoding approach is similar to that used in MAVERICK [15]: each candidate solution is an enumerated set of parameters to be monitored and manipulated. A GA approach would encode each solution as a binary string where bit position represents the parameter-value relationship, and then manipulate the strings through cut-and-splice and mutation operations to create new potential solutions for testing in the simulation environment. The results of the test are used to assign a fitness to each solution and the GA is again used to form a new population of candidate solutions and the cycle continues [18].

The other encoding technique involves the use of condition-action rules (productions). Genetic algorithm systems using this approach are known as *classifier systems* and generally fall into two categories: those that encode entire rule sets into each candidate solution (Pittsburgh systems) and those that encode individual rules as candidate solutions (Michigan systems) [19, 20]. In both approaches, inputs to the system come from the environment as messages, are matched against the condition fields of the rules, and then the matched rules provide candidate actions which the system chooses between. The output of a classifier system is a message that the environment decodes and interprets as a set of actions to perform.

The Pittsburg approach encodes an entire production system into each candidate solution. The population is then a collection of complete production systems. The GA performs cut-and-splice operations within promising production systems to create new ones, and evaluates the fitness of each production system in isolation from the rest. It does not evaluate the fitness of individual rules. On the other hand, in the Michigan approach the candidate solution population can be considered a single production system. The fitness of each individual rule is determined while in competition with all the other rules and genetic op-

erations are applied across the population.

The Pittsburg approach, like DBL, is typically an "off-line" technique falling into the formulate-test-evaluate genre: rule sets are first evolved using a set of input test cases and then the modified rule sets are tested in the target system. Its advantages include potentially quick learning of complex behaviors and the ability to make radical behavioral changes. The Michigan approach appears more conservative, but allows rules to be modified, added, and deleted from the rule set while the system is "on-line." The two main deficiencies with this approach are the potentially slower learning rates and difficulty in learning more complex behaviors [19]. Both of these are areas of active research in the GA community [21, 22, 23].

A number of recent advances in both the fields of genetic algorithms and adaptive machine learning are being examined for application to our research. Hybrid systems incorporating the characteristics of both Pittsburg and Michigan classifier systems have been developed. A good example is the SAMUAL missile evasion system of the Naval Research Laboratory's Artificial Intelligence Center [23]. SAMUAL controls the maneuvers of a greatly simplified simulated fighter aircraft. It uses a symbolic language to define the rules, and manipulates rule sets by exchanging rules between parent rule sets as well as using other genetic operators. The system has been used to develop plans for evading simulated air-to-air missiles, for tracking an adversary aircraft, and for performing some of the actions in a dog fight. Integration of these functions into a more complex and changing environment has yet to be shown. However, other researchers have used multi-agent systems in more complex environments. In particular, research in the areas of robot and animat control is readily applicable [24].

3.2 Research direction

Our genetic algorithm research is currently focused on higher-level control of autonomous agents in the distributed simulation environment. The goal is to determine the feasibility of using hybrid GA approaches for higher-level learning tasks. We are also interested in investigating the ability to use "on-line" learning methods in a real-time complex system interacting with a changing environment.

The prototype will consist of a hybrid classifier system using a multi-agent internal structure. It will control a set of lower-level functional agents that in turn control the operator interface to an existing flight simulation, similar to MAXIM. Although the initial functionality of this system is intended to be primitive, it is anticipated that some network interaction with other nodes in the simulation will be possible (including MAXIM), and will be used to test the learning capability of the system. The use of parallel architectures is anticipated to better approach real-time performance, and two hardware platforms are being used to develop the prototype: a hypercube-based architecture and a distributed workstation network. An initial prototype based on a modified parallel classifier system is currently being tested and is showing promising results. If compatibility and processing time issues can be resolved, the final multi-agent system should

be able to draw upon the tactics data currently in the universal plan as a source of the initial rule set.

4 Conclusion

This paper discusses several approaches for leveraging machine learning technologies to improve the performance/capabilities of autonomous agents within a distributed simulation environment. It provides a description of the two current research thrusts at AFIT that allow the agents to discover improvements through unaided experimentation within a simulation. We anticipate using these approaches as an integral part of the knowledge acquisition process for developing robust, realistic simulation-based air combat adversaries and allies.

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